

A Comprehensive Examination of Potential of Peptides and their Role in Cosmeceuticals

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Abstract: In the field of cosmeceuticals, where pharmaceuticals and cosmetics converge, extensive research is underway to provide robust scientific evidence for the bioactivity of innovative ingredients. Peptides, recognized for their diverse biological roles as signaling and regulatory molecules, are particularly intriguing within this context. They contribute significantly to processes spanning defense, immunity, stress response, growth, homeostasis, and reproduction. The unique qualities of peptides make them ideal bioactive components in cosmeceuticals, meeting the stringent requirements set by the industry for novel formulations. Recent focus has expanded to encompass not only bioactivity but also considerations of bioavailability and stability in peptide-based cosmeceutical formulations. This review explores emerging techniques aimed at enhancing peptide skin penetration and stability, drawing insights from both scholarly literature and industry patents. The cosmetic sector's keen interest in bioactive peptides stems from their potential to elevate skin health and aesthetics. These small protein fragments exhibit a myriad of beneficial biological properties, including anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, antioxidant, and antibacterial effects. Moreover, this review deals with the utilization of bioactive peptides in cosmetics, elucidating their mechanisms of action. These peptides can be sourced from diverse natural reservoirs such as plants, animals, and marine organisms, employing various extraction methods like enzymatic hydrolysis, ultrafiltration, fermentation, and high-performance liquid chromatography. Through comprehensive examination and analysis, this review sheds light on the burgeoning role of peptides in driving innovation within the cosmeceutical industry.

Keywords: Cosmeceuticals; Peptides; Skin Health; Anti-inflammatory; Anti-aging; Antioxidant; Antibacterial; Natural Sources.

1. Introduction

Combining pharmaceuticals with cosmetics, cosmeceuticals incorporate physiologically active compounds aimed at enhancing skin appearance while also providing therapeutic benefits. The term "cosmetic" derives from the Greek word "kosm tikos," signifying "power, arranging, and decorating skill," highlighting the historical narrative of cosmetic development. Defined by the Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940, cosmetics encompass articles intended for application to the human body for purposes of cleansing, beautifying, improving attractiveness, or altering appearance. Bioactive cosmeceutical components offer appealing qualities such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, skin-whitening, anti-aging, or anti-wrinkling effects. Typically administered topically, cosmetics include creams, ointments, and lotions. [1-4] Skin issues, increasingly prevalent across all age groups, often stem from exposure to chemical agents, biological toxins, and microbes. Advancements in science and technology have propelled the evolution of bioactive cosmeceuticals, meeting consumer demand for products that not only enhance beauty but also promote overall skin health. Peptides, potent yet minuscule molecules, have emerged as transformative agents within this industry, reshaping skincare practices. Formerly confined to biochemistry and medical research, peptides are now prized as superior bioactive compounds in cosmetics. Comprising short chains of amino acids, the fundamental units of numerous biological processes, peptides play pivotal roles in physiology and biochemistry. While their significance has long been recognized, their application in cosmetics has recently gained momentum, facilitated by advancements in synthesis and formulation techniques. Peptides exert influence over various skin-related processes, including protein synthesis and regulation, inflammation, angiogenesis, melanogenesis, cell motility, proliferation, and migration. Leveraging ligand binding as their primary mechanism of action, peptides exhibit remarkable sequence and structural diversity, manifesting a wide array of effects. Moreover, peptides predominantly consist of natural L-amino acids, minimizing immunogenicity and facilitating rapid breakdown into individual amino acids. [5, 6] The synthesis process is both straightforward and scalable, with the type and quantity of amino acids significantly impacting production costs. [7]

Bioactive or topical peptides, though synthetic, are composed of modified amino acid chains aimed at enhancing existing physiological functions, such as improving skin permeability, stability, solubility, and interaction with cell receptors. The initiation

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and regulation of numerous natural physiological processes often hinge on interactions with specific amino acid sequences found in peptides and protein fragments. The concept of youth is closely intertwined with perceptions of beauty, leading to the incorporation of various peptides into anti-aging treatments within the cosmetics industry. Consequently, skin-enhancing cosmetics have gained popularity among both genders. External factors like smoke combine with endogenous mechanisms such as oxidative stress, resulting in oxidative damage to skin cells and subsequent aging. Maintaining a healthy balance between the synthesis and degradation of structural proteins like collagen is crucial in altering the skin's biological clock, a principle underpinning many collagen turnover-controlling products on the market. [8]

Another approach suggested for reducing fine lines and wrinkles associated with aging involves temporarily enhancing skin firmness through the inhibition or stimulation of specific neurotransmitters. However, caution is advised regarding the association between high-quality topical care products and dietary supplements, as the term "peptide" is increasingly applied to largely unexplained hydrolysates. [9-12] Modern consumers, particularly women, recognize the importance of scrutinizing ingredient lists and product labels (International Nomenclature of Cosmetic Ingredients, or INCI), driven by a desire for transparency regarding the active ingredients in cosmeceuticals. Unlike makeup, cosmeceuticals contain active components with scientifically proven benefits. Peptides primarily function by stimulating the production of essential proteins crucial for skin structure and function, such as collagen and elastin, which diminish with age, leading to sagging, wrinkles, and loss of firmness. With the appropriate structure, peptides can promote the synthesis of these proteins and mimic their actions, resulting in the appearance of younger, smoother skin

Figure 1. Commonly used peptides in cosmeceuticals

2. Diverse applications of peptides in cosmeceuticals

Peptides in cosmeceuticals encompass a broad spectrum of types, each tailored to address specific skin concerns. Their selection within skincare products is guided by their unique characteristics and modes of action [13-17]

2.1. Collagen boosting peptides

These bioactive peptides are utilized in skincare and cosmeceutical formulations to stimulate collagen production, a vital protein responsible for skin firmness, suppleness, and structure. As natural collagen synthesis diminishes with age, resulting in fine lines, wrinkles, and sagging skin, collagen-boosting peptides work to enhance overall skin health and combat these issues. The common examples of collagen boosting Copper Tripeptide-1, Palmitoyl Tetrapeptide-7. Applications include Serums, creams, masks targeting skin aging and promoting youthful appearance. [18]

2.2. Anti-Aging Peptides

Designed to counteract signs of skin aging, anti-aging peptides induce various cellular activities that support a more youthful complexion. Their primary mode of action often involves promoting collagen formation and muscle relaxation, reducing the visibility of wrinkles and fine lines. Examples are Argireline (Acetyl Hexapeptide-8), Palmitoyl Pentapeptide-3. Functions include reducing muscle tension in the face, minimizing wrinkles and fine lines. [19, 20]

2.3. Hydration Peptides

Peptides formulated for hydration purposes aim to enhance skin moisture retention and overall hydration levels. By improving water retention, reinforcing the skin barrier, and reducing trans-epidermal water loss (TEWL), these peptides contribute to smoother, more hydrated skin. Examples include Palmitoyl Pentapeptide-4, Acetyl Hexapeptide-37. Benefits of hydration peptides are increased moisture retention, smoother skin texture. [21]

2.4. Antioxidant Peptides

Comprising short amino acid sequences with antioxidant properties, these peptides neutralize free radicals, protecting skin cells from oxidative damage and premature aging. Common examples include glutathione and glutathione-like peptides, often integrated into various skincare products for enhanced efficacy. Antioxidant Peptides: Glutathione, Glutathione-like peptides Usage: Sunscreens, moisturizers, serums for environmental protection. [22]

2.5. Brightening Peptides

Brightening peptides target hyperpigmentation, dark spots, and uneven skin tone by inhibiting melanin synthesis or its transport to the skin's outer layers. Oligopeptide-68 and nonapeptide-1 are among the peptides utilized to address pigmentation issues and promote a more uniform complexion. Brightening Agents: Oligopeptide-68, Nonapeptide-1. Actions: Minimizing dark spots, promoting even skin tone. [23]

2.6. Repair and Healing Peptides

Incorporated into cosmeceuticals to facilitate skin repair, wound healing, and overall skin health, repair and healing peptides expedite natural healing processes. Copper peptides, notably GHK-Cu, are recognized for their ability to reduce inflammation, enhance skin elasticity, and promote collagen synthesis. Repair Peptides: GHK-Cu (Copper Peptides). Applications: Serums, creams, ointments for scar treatment and skin renewal. [24]

3. Advantages and limitations of peptides in cosmeceuticals

3.1. Advantages

- Regulation of Physiological Processes: Peptides play pivotal roles in various skin-related physiological processes, including cell division, migration, inflammation, angiogenesis, melanogenesis, and protein synthesis and regulation. [25]
- High Selectivity: Peptides demonstrate excellent selectivity due to their ability to establish multiple interactions with specific targets, leading to reduced toxicity and adverse effects. [25]
- Natural Composition: Peptides primarily consist of naturally occurring L-amino acids, which undergo metabolism over time to yield individual amino acids. They are generally non-immunogenic, enhancing their safety profile. [25]
- Cosmetic Flexibility: As cosmetics are not subject to pre-market approval requirements by regulatory agencies like the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), peptide-based formulations offer flexibility in product development and innovation [25]

3.2. Limitations

- Testing Methods: Evaluation of cosmetic products often relies on in vitro testing using silicon skin clones, which may not fully replicate human skin physiology. [26]
- Limited Research: Cosmetic companies typically conduct small-scale, open-label studies on peptides, which may limit comprehensive understanding of their efficacy and safety.
- Cost Considerations: The cost of peptides is influenced by the type and quantity of amino acids required for synthesis, with certain amino acids being more expensive than others. [27]

- **Transdermal Challenges:** Peptides face challenges related to transdermal distribution and efficacy due to their high molecular weight, limited lipophilicity, and potential interactions with other substances. Achieving optimal skin penetration remains a significant hurdle in peptide-based cosmeceutical formulations [28]

4. Classification and functions of peptides in cosmeceuticals

Peptides in cosmeceuticals are categorized into several groups based on their distinct properties and functions, each contributing uniquely to skincare formulations.

4.1. Signal Peptides

Signal peptides stimulate skin fibroblasts, promoting the synthesis of collagen and elastic fibers. These peptides mimic signals involved in extracellular matrix (ECM) protein production, enhancing overall skin health and appearance. [30]

4.1.1 Structure: Signal peptides comprise polar carboxyl-terminal, hydrophobic core, and positively charged amino-terminal domains.

4.1.2 Mechanism: They activate protein kinase C, promoting cell growth, migration, and collagen synthesis.

4.1.3 Examples: Palmitoyl peptides, such as palmitoyl tripeptide-1 (Pal-GHK), and palmitoyl tripeptide-5 (Pal-KTTKS), stimulate collagen synthesis and reduce aging signs. [31]

4.2. Carrier Peptides

Carrier peptides facilitate the transportation of essential substances, particularly trace elements like copper (Cu) and manganese (Mn), crucial for wound healing and enzymatic functions.

4.2.1 Function: Cu-GHK (Copper tripeptide-1) supports collagen synthesis, skin regeneration, and wound healing. [32]

4.2.2 Effectiveness: Clinical studies demonstrate Cu-GHK's efficacy in enhancing skin elasticity, thickness, and moisture content.

4.3. Neurotransmitter-Inhibitory Peptides

These peptides target muscular contraction methods controlled by neurotransmitters, effectively reducing wrinkles and fine lines.

4.3.1 Examples: Acetyl Hexapeptide-3 (Argireline) and Pentapeptide-18 (Leuphasyl) mimic botulinum toxin, inhibiting neurotransmitter release and muscle contraction. [33]

4.3.2 Efficacy: Clinical trials confirm their anti-wrinkle effects, reducing wrinkle size and depth significantly.

4.4. Enzyme Inhibitory Peptides

Peptides in this category directly or indirectly block enzyme activity, offering various skincare benefits.

4.4.1 Sources: Soy oligopeptides, rice-derived peptides, and silk fibroin peptides exhibit enzyme inhibitory properties.

4.4.2 Effects: Soy oligopeptides protect against UVB-induced photodamage, rice-derived peptides reduce MMP activity and melanogenesis, while silk fibroin peptides demonstrate anti-inflammatory and antioxidant actions. [34]

Figure 2. Classification of peptides

5. Sources of peptides

Bioactive peptides with promising cosmetic properties can be obtained through natural sources or chemical synthesis. Various extraction methods are employed to derive peptides from natural sources, including plants, animals, and marine environments, offering a diverse range of functional peptide architectures [35]

5.1. Plant derived peptides

Plants contain proteins with high levels of beneficial chemicals, such as anti-diabetic, anti-hypertensive, antimicrobial, and antioxidant characteristics. Peptides derived from plants undergo chemical or enzymatic hydrolysis of larger proteins to create blends of protein fragments tailored to desired biological functions [35].

5.1.1. Antioxidant and antimicrobial properties

Plant-derived peptides possess notable cosmetic advantages, with some exhibiting antimicrobial properties against a wide range of bacteria.

5.1.2. Examples

Enzymatically hydrolyzed oat bran peptides have demonstrated antioxidant properties and the ability to reduce oxidative stress-induced cell damage, potentially preventing UV-induced skin damage. [36]

5.2. Animal derived peptides

Peptides derived from animals, including milk, fish, eggs, and meat, are gaining popularity in the cosmetics industry due to their diverse functional properties. Sources include animal-derived peptides are commonly found in milk proteins, with additional sources including fish, eggs, and meat. Production: Enzymes from native, microbial, and environmental sources transform animal proteins into physiologically-active peptides during milk secretion, processing, and digestion [37]

5.3. Marine derived peptides

Peptides derived from marine sources offer outstanding nutritional and cosmetic benefits, showcasing antibacterial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and neuroprotective properties. Bioactivities include marine peptides exhibit various bioactivities, including anticancer effects, apoptotic induction, angiogenesis inhibition, and cytotoxicity against cancer cells. Example: Algicidal peptides isolated from marine fungi and cyclic lipopeptides from marine sponges demonstrate antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities against harmful algae and cancer cells, respectively [38]

5.4. Safety assessment of bioactive peptides

As demand for cosmeceutical products grows, ensuring the safety of cosmetic peptides becomes crucial. Regulatory bodies like the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) assess the safety of cosmetic ingredients based on their effectiveness and minimal risk of adverse effects. Safety Considerations comprise of cosmetic peptides must be safe for use without causing skin toxicity, sensitization, or irritation, while still providing observable skin benefits. Regulatory Compliance: Cosmetic peptides, such as palmitoyl pentapeptide-4, are deemed safe within specified concentration limits by regulatory authorities, ensuring consumer safety in skincare formulations [39]

6. Conclusion

The efficacy of cosmetic products in addressing skin concerns such as hyperpigmentation, wrinkles, aging, and rough skin texture can be significantly enhanced by incorporating bioactive peptides. These peptides, derived from various sources including plants, animals, marine organisms, and edible insects, exhibit multifunctional cosmetic attributes such as anti-aging, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties. Numerous *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, as well as clinical trials, have demonstrated the effectiveness of bioactive peptides in improving skin appearance through both topical and oral administration, leveraging distinct intracellular processes. However, further research is needed to fully understand their mechanisms of action and potential synergies with other active ingredients commonly found in cosmetic formulations. Many clinical trials have shown promising results, but some limitations exist, including the use of small sample sizes and formulations containing peptides alongside other active ingredients, making it challenging to isolate the precise contribution of peptides to observed skin benefits. Moreover, while certain peptides like Cu-GHK have been extensively studied, there is ongoing research to explore their effectiveness and potential new modes of action. Additionally, while anti-aging properties are a primary focus, further investigation is warranted to explore the diverse applications of bioactive peptides in skincare. Overall, bioactive peptides hold promise as both therapeutic agents for enhancing skin health and functional components in complementary skincare treatments for various dermatological conditions.

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